

KOLEGJI AAB

FAKULTETI I GJUHËS ANGLEZE

PROGRAMI MASTER

**The Effect of the English Language Use on the
Cultural Identity of Kosovar Gen Z: A Sociolinguistic
Study**

Candidate:

Bardha Shkodra

Mentor:

Prof. Asoc. Dr. Aleksandar Takovski

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Acknowledgments

“Hard work is worthless for those that don’t believe in themselves.” – Naruto Uzumaki

I begin my acknowledgments with heartfelt gratitude to God, whose unwavering support and guidance have been my anchor throughout the past five years. My deepest thanks go to my beloved parents, whose boundless love, encouragement, and sacrifices have fueled my perseverance.

I extend a sincere tribute to my esteemed professors at the university, whose expertise and dedication have not only imparted knowledge but also nurtured my growth and resilience, inspiring me to reach for the highest aspirations.

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As I reflect on this journey, I embark on the next chapter of my life with confidence and determination, ready to face new challenges and pursue further growth and success.

Abstract

This thesis investigates the attitudes and behaviors of Generation Z individuals towards English language usage in Kosovo and its impact on their cultural identity. Through a mixed-methods approach involving surveys and interviews, the study aims to understand the frequency and type of English language use among Generation Z, as well as their perceptions and feelings towards its influence on their cultural identity. The research objectives include identifying attitudes towards English language use, documenting its frequency and type of usage, and comparing its influence on cultural identity between Generation Z and Generation X. Findings reveal a significant preference for English language use among Generation Z, particularly facilitated by online platforms and media. However, concerns about the potential erosion of Albanian cultural identity are raised, highlighting the need for further research and consideration of language policies and education strategies. This study contributes to the understanding of language attitudes and behaviors among younger generations in Kosovo and underscores the importance of language in shaping cultural identity in a globalized world.

Abstrakti

Ky disertacion hulumton qëndrimet dhe sjelljet e individëve të Gjeneratës Z kundrejt përdorimit të gjuhës angleze në Kosovë dhe ndikimin që ajo ka pasur në identitetin kulturor të tyre. Përmes një qasjeje me metoda të ndryshme duke përfshirë sondazhe dhe intervista, studimi synon të kuptojë frekuencën dhe llojin e përdorimit të gjuhës angleze midis Gjeneratës Z, si dhe perceptimet dhe ndjenjat e tyre në lidhje me ndikimin e saj në identitetin e tyre kulturor. Objektivat e hulumtimit përfshijnë identifikimin e qëndrimeve ndaj përdorimit të gjuhës angleze, dokumentimin e frekuencës dhe llojit të përdorimit të saj, dhe krahasimin e ndikimit të saj në identitetin kulturor mes Gjeneratës Z dhe Gjeneratës X. Gjetjet zbulojnë një preferencë të rëndësishme për përdorimin e gjuhës angleze midis Gjeneratës Z, veçanërisht të lehtësuar nga platformat online dhe media. Megjithatë, shqetësime në lidhje me erodimin potencial të identitetit kulturor shqiptar ngriten, duke nënvizuar nevojën për hulumtime të mëtejshme dhe konsideratë të politikave gjuhësore dhe strategjive të arsimit. Ky studim kontribuon në kuptimin e qëndrimeve dhe sjelljeve gjuhësore në mesin e brezave të rinj në Kosovë dhe nënvizon rëndësinë e gjuhës në formimin e identitetit kulturor në një botë të globalizuar.

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Chapter I

Introduction

1. Background

In contemporary Kosovo, the English language holds significant sway. Beyond its inclusion in formal education from an early age, English permeated everyday discourse and activities, emerging as an indispensable skill requisite for keeping pace with modern trends, particularly among Generation Z.

This generational cohort represents among the first to be raised in an environment consistently exposed to the English language, setting them apart from previous generations, such as Generation X, who typically acquired English proficiency to a lesser extent, primarily through formal schooling.

Language, as a phenomenon, undoubtedly plays a role into the psych of an individual (Jackendoff, 2002), thus playing a pivotal role in shaping one's identity. The crux of the matter lies in discerning which aspects of identity are impacted by language use.

Identity is very complex notion that covers multiple aspects of who we are, based on which, what we think, how we talk and how we interact with one another. Among the plethora of definitions of identity, since my focus on this study is based on the cultural identity of different generations, I found the following the most useful. (Chen. Key concept no.22, 2014), "Cultural identity refers to identification with, or sense of belonging to, a particular group based on various cultural categories, including nationality, ethnicity, race, gender, and religion. Cultural identity is constructed and maintained through the process of sharing collective knowledge, such as traditions, heritage, language, aesthetics, norms and customs."

The cultural category this research addresses is age, in particular, a generational cohort born between 1996 and 2010, with its own distinctive style of language, lifestyle, morals, customs and beliefs.

Identity is, in fact, a very complicated thematic, but in simple terms, it is defined as the characteristics that determine who or what a person is. It refers to the ways we talk that make us differ from others, the ways we interact with others, the way we do things, along with our core beliefs and values, that make us member of a particular group.

These are the cultural identity markers that I have taken as measuring units to ascertain the role of English language, as one such marker, upon the remaining markers constitutive of the complexity called identity.

Omoniyi & Goodith (2006) explain that bilinguals may simply by an act of codeswitching, repositioning or aligning themselves with other group ('s identity) different from the one they had seemed to claim leading up to the moment of switching.

This understanding is most applicable in the case of my research, because as in many other countries, in Kosovo as well, Generation Z is considered to be the generation of globalization, since it was born and raised throughout the years when technological advancements have brought the world closer together.

An addition to this was the international presence in Kosovo from 1999, which acted as an agent of globalization and played a role in the “westernization” of Gen Z, a generation that consists of individuals whose English language proficiency is in a high level.

This study will be explaining how Kosovar Gen Z uses English language, when, why, and if this use forms a significant part of the cultural identity different from the cultural identities of the previous generations, especially Gen X.

1.1. Topic area

This comprehensive study delves deeply into the multifaceted impact of the English language on the cultural identity of Generation Z in Kosovo. It seeks to elucidate the profound role that English has assumed as a conduit for the infiltration of global trends and Western ideologies into the fabric of contemporary Kosovar youth culture. Through an exhaustive analysis, this research endeavors to uncover the intricate mechanisms through which the pervasive presence of English language has reshaped the collective identity of Generation Z, setting them apart from the preceding generations.

Indeed, this phenomenon represents a significant departure from the cultural norms and values entrenched in older generations, highlighting the transformative power of linguistic globalization on societal structures and individual identity formation. By examining the nuances interaction between language, culture, and identity, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the evolving sociolinguistic landscape of Kosovo, shedding light on the dynamic processes shaping the cultural identity of its youth population.

1.2. Statement of research problem and justification

Language attitudes have been widely recognized as influential factors shaping behavioral patterns, particularly during social interactions. Individuals who harbor positive attitudes towards a language are inclined to utilize it more frequently, thereby fostering greater linguistic engagement and cooperativeness in social contexts.

Moreover, language serves as a multifaceted medium through which individuals express various aspects of their identity. It not only dictates how individuals communicate with each other, but also plays a pivotal role in shaping their cultural identity. Language is intricately intertwined with culture, serving as a vehicle for the transmission of values, beliefs, and customs across generations. As asserted by Bryam (2006), language serves a vital social function, fostering a sense of group identity and solidarity by facilitating communication of shared cultural norms and traditions.

Therefore, it follows that the pervasive use of the English language among Generation Z in Kosovo holds significant implications for their perception of the world and the construction of their identity. As Generation Z continuously engages with English as a medium of communication, it inadvertently exposes them to new perspectives and values, acting as a conduit for the adoption of globalized norms and ideologies. This ongoing interaction with the English language not only reflects a generational shift in linguistic preferences but also signifies a broader transformation in cultural attitudes and worldview among Kosovar youth.

1.3. Objectives

The objectives of this study were:

1. To identify the attitudes that Generation Z has towards English language use.
2. To document the type and the frequency of English language use by this generation in Kosovo.
3. To pinpoint if the attitudes of Generation Z towards English language and its use, have indeed played a role in their cultural identity in comparison to Gen X's.

1.4. Focus and scope

According to the population register compiled by the Agency of Statistics of Kosovo (ASK) in 2011, the total number of individuals born between 1996 and 2010 amounts to 662,509. In relative terms, this demographic segment, known as Generation Z (Gen Z), constitutes approximately one-third of the overall population of Kosovo.

Notably, Generation Z is characterized by unique attributes stemming from their upbringing amidst rapid technological advancements and evolving societal norms.

Compared to their predecessors, Generation X, members of Gen Z exhibit distinct lifestyle preferences and possess notably higher proficiency in the English language. Consequently, this research focuses specifically on the attitudes and characteristics of Generation Z, recognizing them as representative of a cohort with a distinct sociocultural characteristics and linguistic competencies.

1.5. Conceptual framework

The foundational framework of this study is predicated upon three core concepts: attitude, linguistic behavior, and cultural identity.

Attitude, as conceptualized herein, denoted a settled disposition or inclination towards a particular subject of phenomenon. It encompasses individuals' thoughts and feelings towards a given entity, influencing their subsequent actions and behaviors.

Linguistic behavior, on the other hand, encompasses the array of actions and practices undertaken by individuals who engage in language use. It encompasses verbal and nonverbal interactions, language choices, and communicative strategies employed within social contexts.

Cultural identity, a pivotal aspect of this study, refers to the sense of belonging and identification with a specific cultural group. It is shaped by various cultural categories, including language, ethnicity, nationality, and shared cultural norms and values.

Central to this research is the exploration of how the attitudes of Generation Z towards the English language impact the frequency and extent of its usage. Additionally, this study seeks to elucidate how such linguistic behavior influences the cultural identity of Generation Z, encompassing variables such as cultural norms, values, morals, and lifestyle choices. This investigation will be juxtaposed with similar dynamics observed within Generation X, facilitating a comparative analysis of generational shifts in linguistic attitudes and their implications for cultural identity formation. Through a nuanced examination of these interrelated concepts, this study endeavors to offer valuable insights into the evolving sociolinguistic landscape and cultural dynamics within Kosovo.

1.6. Research questions

This study has aimed to answer the following research questions:

1. What attitudes does Gen Z hold towards English language?
2. How do Gen Z's attitudes affect the amount, scope and the context of English language used by this generation?
3. What difference does Gen Z's cultural identity has in comparison to the cultural identity of Gen X, and whether this is affected by the knowledge, exposure and use of English?

1.7. Hypothesis

This study hypothesized that:

1. The attitudes of Gen Z towards English language are expected to be positive, and in return, these positive attitudes affect English language use, which directly affects the patterns of cultural identification.
2. A positive attitude towards English language is going to result in a continuous usage of this language, and continuous use will affect cultural identification.
3. Gen Z's cultural identity is more "globalized" and more affected by the western, mostly Anglo-Saxon cultures, in comparison to Gen X's, as a result of a continuous usage and exposure of English language.

Chapter II

Literature Review

2. Introduction

This thematic review encompasses an extensive compilation of scholarly studies, each offering detailed insight into the nuanced interplay between language attitudes, individual and group behaviors, and their profound implications for identity formation. While the correlation between attitudes towards language and their influence on behavior, including the broader construct of identity, has been explored in previous research, the specific examination of these dynamics within the context of distinct generational cohorts in Kosovo remains notably underexplored.

In light of this gap in the existing literature, this chapter undertakes a rigorous analysis of research findings from various global contexts. By synthesizing and contextualizing these diverse perspectives, this study endeavors to shed light on the local sociolinguistic landscape of Kosovo, offering a clearer understanding of how language attitudes shape behavior and cultural identity, particularly within specific generational cohorts. Through this comparative approach, the aim is to elucidate the unique dynamics at play within Kosovo while drawing upon the rich body of existing research to inform and enrich our understanding of these complex interactions.

2.1. Attitudes and language use

When considering the concept of attitude, it becomes apparent that it encompasses a broad spectrum of feelings and thoughts individuals hold towards various aspects of their environment. Simplistically speaking, attitudes can be understood as the mental dispositions individuals develop or form in response to individuals, actions, or phenomena they encounter. These attitudes often manifest as either positive or negative, representing individuals' predispositions towards specific entities.

As posited by Allport (1935), attitude is not merely a passive state of mind, but rather a dynamic and directive force shaped by individuals' experiences and temperament. It serves as a cognitive framework that guides individuals' responses to the myriad objects and situations they encounter in their daily lives. In essence, attitudes can be constructed as mental predispositions or tendencies that influence individuals' behaviors, as articulated by Jeffrey (2005).

Another pertinent perspective on attitude is provided by Ajzen and Cote (2010), who assert that attitudes are reflective of individuals' cognitive processing of information they have been exposed to. They serve as the cognitive foundation from which people respond to objects and events in their surroundings. In the context of this study, language serves as a crucial phenomenon through which attitudes are shaped and expressed.

The manner in which individuals process the abstract construct of language significantly influences their attitudes towards it, whether positive or negative. Furthermore, attitudes are not limited to language in general but also extend to the use of specific language.

In the case of this study focusing on Kosovar youth, particular attention is directed towards attitudes surrounding the use of the English language.

Empirical research conducted by Lohaj (2018) sheds light on the linguistic landscape among Kosovo youth, revealing significant levels of proficiency in English among various demographic groups. The prevalence of English proficiency among Kosovar youth surpasses national averages, indicating a prevailing positive attitude towards the English language. This observation lays the groundwork for further exploration and substantiation of Generation Z's attitudes towards English language use in Kosovo.

2.2. Attitudes and behavior

Numerous scholarly inquiries, including the work of M. Dragojevic (2017), have posited that language exerts a considerable influence on behavioral cooperativeness during social interactions. When individuals harbor positive attitudes towards a particular phenomenon, such as language, they are inclined to utilize it more frequently. This continuous engagement with the language inevitable shaped their behavioral responses over time.

To delve deeper into the notion of behavior, we turn to the insights provided by the Noldus Team (2003). According to their elucidation, behavior encompasses observable and measurable actions, responses, and activity patterns exhibited by individuals or groups. These behaviors can be categorized into two main distinctions: overt and covert behavior. Overt behavior pertains to external or physical manifestations, while covert behavior involves internal or cognitive processes occurring within an individual's mind.

The latter encompasses various cognitive functions, including memory, perception, thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making activities.

When examining the interplay between language attitudes and behavior, it becomes evident that the impact primarily manifests in covert behavior. While overt behavior is observable and tangible, it is the internal cognitive processes that are significantly influenced by one's attitude towards language use. In the context of this research, the positive attitude held by individuals, particularly Generation Z, towards the use of the English language directly influences their covert behavior. Consequently, they are predisposed to incorporate English into their daily interactions and activities to a greater extent, thereby shaping their linguistic behavior patterns. This continuous engagement with English language usage serves as a pivotal determinant in shaping the behavioral tendencies of individuals within this demographic cohort.

2.3. Attitudes, behavior and identity

In addition to the positive correlation observed between attitudes and behavior, there exists a noteworthy relationship between behavior and identity.

Understanding this connection requires a clear grasp of what constitutes a positive correlation.

As delineated by the Indeed Editorial Team (2021), a positive correlation denotes the synchronized operation of two or more variables, wherein changes in one variable correspond with changes in the other. Applied to language attitudes and behavior, this implies that individuals or groups with a positive disposition towards a language are more likely to utilize it extensively. Conversely, a negative attitude towards a language may lead to reduced usage.

In essence, the level of language use acts as manifestation of one's attitude towards it. When individuals exhibit a positive attitude towards a language, their behavior reflects this sentiment through increased usage. Conversely, negative attitudes are typically associated with decreased language usage.

To illustrate, let's consider a scenario where an individual develops a fondness for a particular language. This positive attitude prompts them to engage in frequent language use, thereby reinforcing the correlation between attitude and behavior.

Conversely, if someone harbors negative sentiments towards a language, their reluctance to use it diminishes their overall language usage.

By comprehending the dynamics of this correlation, we gain insight into how language attitudes shape behavior, and in turn, influence identity formation. This interplay underscores their pivotal role that language plays in shaping cultural and individual identities.

Further delving into the positive correlation between behavior, particularly the extensive use of language, and identity, Simons J. D. (2021) expounds upon the Identity Behavior Theory (IBT), asserting, "Identity and Behavior are undoubtedly connected to one another. Behavior does not only mirror the identity of an individual, it also helps develop it."

This insightful perspective underscores the intricate relationship between behavior patterns and formation of one's identity.

Simons' statement prompts us to consider how the covert behavior of Generation Z, influenced by their favorable attitudes towards English language use, contributes to the shaping of their identities. As these individuals exhibit increased language usage in their everyday interactions, it inevitably leaves an imprint on their sense of self and cultural identity.

To elucidate this concept further, it is imperative to delve deeper into the notion of identity. According to H, Kira (2010), identity is not a static construct confined to an individual's psyche; rather, it is a dynamic socio-cultural phenomenon that evolves through social interactions. This perspective challenges the traditional view of identity as an inherent trait and instead positions it as an emergent product shaped by linguistic and other semiotic practices within a social and cultural context.

This study adopts the principle that identity is best understood as a product of ongoing social interactions rather than a pre-existing entity. By recognizing identity as a fluid and multifaceted construct, we acknowledge its complex interplay with language use and cultural practices. This holistic approach allows us to explore how the attitudes and behaviors associated with language use contribute to the construction and negotiation of identity among Generation Z individuals in Kosovo and beyond.

In essence, identity is not merely an inherent psychological construct that individuals possess, but rather a dynamic process shaped by social interactions, particularly through language. Continuous engagement with a language and exposure to diverse social behaviors contribute significantly to the formation and evolution of one's identity over time.

The intertwining relationship between language and identity is a fundamental aspect of human communication, as highlighted by Le Page and Tabouret-Keller (1985). They assert that the language spoken by an individual is inseparable from their identity, emphasizing that language serves as a key marker of cultural belonging and individual expression.

To further illustrate how language and social behavior influence identity formation, consider the case study of Obeng and Adegbija (1999), which examines the language practices of Africans from the southern coast. These individuals, whose native language is Ivorian, found themselves compelled to learn *Français du Treichville*, a simplified form of French, due to political, economic, and social factors. Parents, recognizing the economic opportunities associated with French proficiency, actively encouraged their children to acquire the language as a means of securing a better financial future.

This case study exemplifies how language acquisition and usage are influenced by socio-cultural contexts and economic imperatives, ultimately shaping individuals' identities. By adapting their linguistic practices to navigate societal expectations and opportunities, individuals undergo a transformative process wherein their identity becomes intertwined with their language proficiency and social behaviors. Thus, language serves not only as a medium of communication but also as a vehicle for identity construction and cultural adaptation in diverse social settings.

The emergence of a new generation in certain regions has resulted in shifts in cultural identity, notably exemplified by the case of Ivorians who speak French as their primary

language instead of their native Ivorian tongue. Despite self-identifying as Ivorians, the adoption of French as their native language has inevitably influenced their cultural identity, diverging from that of their ancestors. This transformation underscores the profound impact of language on shaping cultural affiliations and perceptions of belonging.

A similar trend is observed among Generation Z in Indonesia, a culturally diverse nation. A study conducted by Muthiara Dharma et al. (2022), highlights the consequences of globalization and technological advancements on this demographic group. The researches found evidence suggesting that Indonesian Gen Z individuals are increasingly disconnected from their cultural roots, with a diminishing sense of appreciation for local traditions and languages. This erosion of cultural identity is attributed to the pervasive influence of Western ideologies, languages, and lifestyles facilitated by globalization and technology. The finding of the study underscore the complex interplay between language, culture, and identity in contemporary societies. They shed light on the challenges faced by younger generations as they navigate between the pressures of globalization and the preservation of cultural heritage. As societies evolve and become more interconnected, understanding these dynamics becomes crucial for maintaining cultural diversity and promoting intercultural dialogue.

John Edwards (2009) elaborates on the intricate relationship between language, identity, and belonging within speech communities. He suggests that language proficiency plays a pivotal role in shaping individuals' sense of community and belonging. Bilingualism, in particular, introduces complexities in identity formation, as it may or may not indicate dual allegiances or affiliations.

Edward raises pertinent questions about the cognitive and linguistic dynamics of bilingual individuals. He explores whether bilinguals possess distinct and separate linguistic systems, or if their cognitive processes integrate both languages into a cohesive linguistic identity. This discussion underscores the nuanced nature of bilingualism and its implications for identity construction.

Applying Edward's insights to our case study, we can analyze how language proficiency influences the perception of belonging among Kosovars. For instance, an individual who exclusively speaks Albanian is likely to identify strongly with the Albanian-speaking community, aligning their sense of identity with that linguistic group. However, for

Kosovars fluent in both Albanian and English, their sense of belonging may be more complex. They may perceive themselves as part of both the Albanian and English-speaking communities, negotiating dual identities and affiliations.

This illustrates the multifaceted nature of identity formation in multilingual contexts, where individuals navigate between different linguistic and cultural spheres.

Understanding these dynamics is essential for comprehending the diverse ways in which language shapes social identities and community affiliations.

2.4. Generation X – Generation Z

In general, or a globalized point of view, Generation Z and Generation X differ in several aspects, including technology usage, cultural influences, and societal values. Here's an overview of some key differences between the two generations:

- *Technology Usage:* Generation Z, born roughly between the mid- 1990's and early 2010s, is considered the first generation to grow up entirely in the digital age. They are highly adept at using technology, particularly smartphones, social media platforms, and other digital tools (Pew Research Center, 2018). In contrast, Generation X, born between the mid-1960s and early 1980s, came of age during the rise of personal computing but experienced a more gradual introduction to digital technologies compared to their successors.
- *Cultural Influences:* Generation Z has been shaped by a globalized and interconnected world, with access to diverse cultural influences through the internet and social media. They tend to be more open-minded and inclusive, embracing diversity in all its forms (Twenge, 2017). On the other hand, Generation X grew up during a period marked by significant social and political changes, including the end of the Cold War and the rise of globalization (Mannheim, 1997). They may exhibit a more skeptical or pragmatic outlook, shaped by their experiences during this transformative period.
- *Societal Values:* Generation Z is often characterized by their concern for social justice, environmental sustainability, and mental health awareness. They are more likely to prioritize work-life balance, personal fulfillment, and social responsibility in their lives and careers (Rideout & Robb, 2020). In contrast, Generation X is known for their

independence, resilience, and self-reliance, having navigated economic recessions, rapid technological advancements, and shifting social norms during their formative years (Parker & Igielnik, 2020).

Now, focusing on Kosovo, these generational differences may manifest in unique ways within the cultural and socio-economic context of the country:

- *Language and Identity*: In Kosovo, where multilingualism is common due to the country's diverse ethnic and linguistic composition, Generation Z may exhibit greater proficiency in English and other global languages compared to Generation X. This is attributed to increased access to English-language education, global media, and online content (Fukuda et al., 2019). As a result, Generation Z Kosovars may feel more connected to global youth culture and trends, potentially influencing their cultural identity and values.
- *Attitudes Towards Tradition*: Generation X in Kosovo may have a stronger attachment to traditional cultural practices and values, reflecting the influence of historical and cultural factors (Krasniqi, 2015). They may prioritize preserving and celebrating Kosovo's cultural heritage, including language, music, cuisine, and customs. In contrast, Generation Z, influenced by globalized media and cultural trends, may exhibit a more eclectic blend of traditional and modern influences, embracing elements of both local and global culture in their lifestyles and identities.
- *Employment and Economic Outlook*: Generation X in Kosovo may have experienced significant economic challenges and political instability during their formative years, including Kosovo War and its aftermath (Muçaj, 2019). As a result, they may value financial security, stability, and career advancements in their professional lives. In contrast, Generation Z, growing up in a post-war period characterized by economic growth and integration efforts, may have different career aspirations and attitudes towards work, prioritizing flexibility, creativity, and social impact in their career choices.

Chapter III

Methodology

3. Introduction

This study is structured around three primary research questions, each addressing different aspects of the relationship between Generation Z (Gen Z) and the English language, as well as its impact on cultural identity. These questions serve as the foundation for understanding the complex dynamics at play:

1. Attitudes Towards English Language: The first research question delves into the attitudes of Generation Z towards the English language and its usage. This involves exploring how members of Gen Z perceive and interact with English as a global language, including their preferences, attitudes, and motivations for using it.
2. Impact of English Language Use on Cultural Identity: The second research question investigated the extent to which the continuous use of English language by Generation Z influences their cultural identity. This involves examining how language use shapes individuals' sense of belonging, values, and cultural practices, particularly in the context of rapidly globalizing world.
3. Comparison of Cultural Identity Between Generations: The third research question compares the cultural identity of Generation Z to that of Generation X, specifically focusing on the degree of Westernization. This involved analyzing how societal changes, technological advancements, and globalization have influenced the cultural values and behaviors of each generation over time.

To address these research questions comprehensively, a longitudinal approach to data collection was adopted, involving multiple phases and methods. Long-term data collection was deemed necessary to capture the evolving attitudes and behaviors of participants over time.

The data collection process encompassed various methodologies, including surveys, interviews, and document analysis. Surveys were used to gather quantitative data on participants' attitudes and language use, while interviews provided deeper insights into their

perceptions and experiences, and document analysis involved examining relevant texts and materials related to language and culture.

Through these diverse data collection methods, I was able to obtain a rich and nuanced understanding of the research questions. The culmination of these efforts resulted in a comprehensive analysis that shed light on the complex interplay between language, culture, and generational identity among participants.

3.1. Methods

The selection of methods for data collection in this study was a thoughtful process aimed at capturing a comprehensive understanding of the research questions at hand. After careful consideration, a mixed-method approach comprising surveys and interviews was chosen as the most suitable methodology. This decision was made by the recognition of the need to gather both qualitative and quantitative data to address the multifaceted nature of the research questions and provide a more holistic perspective.

Surveys were utilized as a quantitative tool to collect structured data from a large sample of participants. This method allowed for the systematic collection of information on various aspects related to the research questions, such as attitudes towards language use, cultural identity, and demographic characteristics. By administering surveys, the researcher was able to gather data efficiently and analyze trends and patterns across the participant population.

Complementing the survey method, interviews were employed to gather qualitative insights and delve deeper into participants' perspectives, experiences, and attitudes. Through semi-structured interviews, I had the opportunity to explore nuanced themes and gain a deeper understanding of the underlying factors influencing participants' attitudes towards language and cultural identity. This qualitative approach provided valuable context and rich descriptive data that enhanced the overall depth of the study.

The combination of surveys and interviews offered a synergistic approach to data collection, leveraging the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. While surveys provided breadth and statistical rigor, interviews contributed depth and richness to the data analysis process. By triangulating findings from multiple sources, I

was able to corroborate results, identify converging patterns, and gain a more comprehensive understanding of the research phenomena.

Furthermore, the mixed-method approach allowed for methodological triangulation, enhancing the credibility and validity of the study findings. By employing multiple data collection methods, I was able to cross-validate findings and mitigate the limitations inherent in any single method. This methodological rigor strengthened the overall robustness of the study and increased confidence in the research outcomes.

Overall, the selection of surveys and interviews as data collection methods was guided by the aim of providing a comprehensive and nuanced exploration of the research questions. By integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches, this study was able to capture the multifaceted nature of the phenomena under investigation and generate rich insights that contribute to a deeper understanding of the topic.

3.2. Sample and settings

The initial step in the data collection process involved the administration of surveys, which served as a foundational component in guiding subsequent qualitative data gathering efforts, specifically through interviews. The survey instrument was meticulously designed to capture insights into participants' attitudes towards and utilization of the English language, as well as to elucidate distinctions in cultural identity across generations. Questions were strategically crafted to explore various facets of cultural identity, including lifestyle preferences, worldviews, cultural tastes, norms, values, and morals. Additionally, the survey incorporated inquiries regarding acceptance levels towards diverse social groups, such as different family structures, individuals within the LGBTQIA+ community, and those with non-religious affiliations, thereby serving as key variables in assessing intergenerational disparities in cultural norms and beliefs.

To ensure inclusivity and accessibility, the survey was made available in both Albanian and English languages, accommodating participants with varying linguistic proficiencies. This approach aimed to foster broader participation and mitigate language barriers that could potentially exclude non-English-speaking respondents from contributing to the study.

The survey findings provided valuable insights that informed the subsequent phase of data collection, which involved conducting individual interviews with representatives from Generation Z and Generation Y. These interviews were instrumental in delving deeper into the nuances of the survey results and gaining a more nuanced understanding of participants' lived experiences and perceptions regarding the role of the English language in shaping their cultural identity and daily practices.

To facilitate widespread dissemination and reach diverse participant demographics, the questionnaires were disseminated through various online platforms, including social media channels such as Facebook, Instagram, Threads, X, Snapchat, LinkedIn, Viber, and WhatsApp. Additionally, invitations for interviews were extended through similar digital platforms, ensuring a broad and diverse pool of participants. Furthermore, some interviews were conducted in collaboration with students from the Infinit Training Center, fostering engagement with local communities and expanding the scope of participant representation in the study.

3.3. Participants

Originally, this study set out with the modest aim of garnering approximately 100 responses. However, the scope of participant involvement far exceeded expectations, ultimately engaging a total of 422 active participants. Of these, 403 individuals contributed to the questionnaire component, while an additional 19 volunteered to participate in interviews, reflecting a remarkable level of interest and engagement with the research endeavor.

Volunteerism characterized the recruitment process for both the questionnaire and interview segments, reflecting the study's overarching goal of capturing diverse perspectives across various demographic dimensions. Participants hailed from different genders, cities, and generations, each bringing their unique opinions and beliefs to the table. Subsequently, the dataset was stratified into distinct groups based on age differences, facilitating a comprehensive comparative analysis.

A concerted effort was made to ensure diversity and inclusivity in participant recruitment, with invitations disseminated across multiple social media platforms and personal

networks. Prospective interviewees were encouraged to reach out directly to me, to express their interest, facilitating personalized engagement and rapport-building. Additionally, eight interview participants volunteered their participation, further enriching the diversity of perspectives represented in the study.

Notably, the recruitment strategy extended to collaborative partnerships with educational institutions, specifically the Infinit Training Center, where additional interviews and focus groups were conducted. These sessions targeted students aged 14 to 18, broadening the demographic spectrum and enhancing the study's richness.

Given the study's comparative focus on generational differences, meticulous attention was paid to ensuring distinction across age cohorts. Specifically, efforts were made to delineate responses from Generation Z (comprising 250 participants), Generation Y (112 participants), and Generation X (41 participants), thereby enabling a nuanced examination of intergenerational dynamics. Additionally, the interview component encompassed 17 individuals from Generation Z, with two participants identified as baby Millennials, further enhancing the study's depth and breadth.

3.4. Data processing and analysis

The analysis of the collected data was conducted through a systematic and meticulous process, with each instrument being examined separately to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the findings.

Initially, the survey data, which was administered in both English and Albanian languages, underwent a merging process to consolidate responses from participants across both versions. Subsequently, the merged dataset was meticulously sorted into four distinct categories based on the generational cohorts to which the participants belonged. This segmentation allowed for a focused examination of responses within each generational group, enabling a nuanced understanding of how attitudes and practices vary across different age demographics.

In contrast, the analysis of the interview data followed a different approach. Unlike the survey responses, the interview transcripts were not segmented into predefined categories. Instead, they were subjected to a deductive approach, wherein themes and patterns

emerged organically from the narratives provided by the participants. This approach facilitated a deeper exploration of individual perspectives and experiences without imposing preconceived categories, thereby allowing for a more nuanced interpretation of the qualitative data.

3.5. Ethical considerations

The process of obtaining informed consent from participants was conducted meticulously to ensure ethical standards were upheld throughout the research endeavor.

For online interviews, participants were presented with an interview consent form, which was read aloud to them, outlining the purpose of the study, the confidentiality measures in place, and their rights as participants. Following the explanation, participants verbally agreed to the conditions outlined in the consent form. In contrast, for in-person interviews, participants were provided with a written consent form, which they read and signed themselves. Additionally, in the case of interviews conducted at the training center, where managerial oversight was present, a consent form was also signed by the center's manager to affirm their approval of the research activities conducted on-site.

In the case of the survey, participants were informed of the voluntary nature of their participation and were assured that their responses would remain anonymous. This information was conveyed to participants through the description provided on the Google Forms website, emphasizing that they were not required to sign in with their Gmail accounts and that their responses would be collected anonymously. This approach was implemented to uphold participant confidentiality and encourage honest and candid responses to the survey questions.

Chapter IV

Results

4. Introduction

This chapter presents the comprehensive analysis of the data collected from both surveys and interviews, providing valuable insights into the attitudes and behaviors of Generation Z towards the English language and its impact on cultural variables.

The data has been meticulously analyzed manually and is presented in a clear and accessible manner through illustrative tables, facilitating better understanding for readers. The first subsection delves into the attitudes of Generation Z towards the English language and its utilization. This includes an in-depth examination of their perceptions, preferences, and overall disposition towards English, shedding light on the role it plays in their lives. Moving on to the second subsection, the focus shifts to exploring the type and frequency of English language usage among Generation Z. This section provides valuable insights into how often and in what contexts Generation Z individuals engage with the English language in their daily lives.

The third and final subsection delves into the correlation between cultural variables, such as attitudes towards LGBTIQ+ individuals, non-religious individuals, and traditional Albanian households, and the influence of English language proficiency. This includes analyzing the impact of English language usage on these cultural variables, taking into account respondents' practices and perceptions.

Furthermore, this subsection extends its analysis by comparing the survey results of other generational cohorts, providing a broader perspective on how attitudes towards the English language vary across different age groups.

To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the results, insights from the interviews are integrated throughout the chapter, particularly emphasizing their relevance within the context of cultural identity formation and perception.

4.1. Attitudes of Gen Z towards English language and its use

In order to gauge the attitudes of Generation Z towards the English language and its utilization, a multifaceted approach was adopted, encompassing both survey-based inquiries and interview-based discussions.

The survey component involved posing indirect questions to participants, designed to elicit insights into their attitudes and perceptions regarding English language usage. These questions explored various aspects, including how participants feel when using English compared to their native tongue, their views on the importance of English language proficiency in contemporary Kosovo, and their perceptions of the ongoing influence of the English language in the country.

Furthermore, during the interview sessions, participants engaged in open discussions about their reactions and sentiments regarding English language use and proficiency. These discussions provided a more nuanced understanding of participants' perspectives, allowing for deeper exploration of their attitudes towards the English language within the context of their daily lives and experiences.

By employing both survey-based inquiries and interview-based discussions, this study was able to comprehensively capture the attitudes of Generation Z towards the English language, offering valuable insights into their perceptions, preferences, and experiences related to English language usage.

4.1.1. How the participants feel while using English language instead of their native tongue, and vice – versa.

To comprehensively assess the inquiry at hand, a combination of surveys and interviews was employed to gather relevant data.

The initial questions in both the Albanian and English language surveys were open-ended, allowing participants to provide free-form responses. These responses were then meticulously categorized into distinct sections based on the themes and meanings conveyed by the participants. Following this, subsequent questions in the surveys were designed to elicit direct responses based on predefined options, providing further insights into participants' attitudes and perspectives.

By utilizing a combination of open-ended and structured survey questions, this approach enabled a comprehensive exploration of participants' views and experiences, contributing valuable insights to the assessment of the inquiry.

The data gathered from a total of 250 participants, comprising 152 respondents who completed the survey in Albanian and 98 in English, all belonging to Generation Z, yielded the following findings:

Table 1 – Why did you choose filling out this questionnaire in the Albanian version, instead of English?

Among the 152 respondents who completed the survey in Albanian, the most common reason cited for using Albanian as opposed to English was "Because I'm Albanian / It is my mother tongue." Following closely behind were responses indicating "No reason," "It's easier," and "I don't speak English." These findings suggest that a significant portion of respondents preferred using Albanian due to their cultural identity and linguistic background, while others cited practical reasons such as familiarity and language proficiency.

Table 2 – Why did you choose filling out this questionnaire in the English version, instead of Albanian?

Among the 98 respondents who completed the survey in English, the most common reason cited for using English over Albanian was “It’s easier.” Following this response were reasons such as “No reason”, “Because I know English”, “I like English better”, and “Because of curiosity”. These feelings suggest that ease of use was the primary factor influencing the choice of English over Albanian, while other factors included proficiency in English, personal preference, and curiosity about the language.

To gain deeper insights into participants' preferences, they were asked during the interviews whether they found it easier to communicate and express their feelings and thoughts in Albanian or English. One participant, identified as interviewee no. 12, expressed that they found it easier to do so in English due to the language's extensive vocabulary, allowing them to precisely articulate their emotions. Another participant, interviewee no. 17, attributed their comfort with English to their frequent consumption of online content, such as social media and movies, in the English language. As a result, they felt more at ease expressing themselves in English and described using Albanian as "cringe-worthy" due to their familiarity with English media. These responses highlight the influence of language exposure and vocabulary richness on individuals' comfort and proficiency in expressing themselves.

4.1.1.1. How does it make you feel using English language rather than your native tongue?

Table 3 – How does it make you feel using English language rather than your native tongue?

In analyzing the responses, it was found that the majority of participants, accounting for 31%, reported feeling "More Fun" when using English language instead of their mother tongue. Following closely behind, 25.5% expressed feeling "Independent" in their English language usage. Additionally, 21% of respondents indicated that using English language made them feel "More Intellectual," while 10% reported feeling "More Important." A smaller portion, 8%, stated feeling "None of the above," while 4.5% noted "Other" feelings, with the predominant sentiment being that it did not evoke any particular difference in emotions.

Delving deeper into these findings during the interviews, participants were asked whether using English language instead of Albanian made them feel more fun or independent. Interviewee no. 15 emphasized the transformative impact of English proficiency on their personality, attributing it to opportunities for international engagement and competition participation. They noted feeling smarter and more independent as a result of their fluency in English. Echoing this sentiment, interviewee no. 12 highlighted the role of English language proficiency in staying abreast of social

media trends and understanding concepts in computer games. They emphasized that English speakers are often perceived as more fun and up-to-date with contemporary culture. These perspectives underscore the multifaceted effects of English language use on individuals' perceptions of themselves and their social interactions.

4.1.2. What does Gen Z think about the importance that a high English language proficiency has nowadays in Kosovo

The matter of what Gen Z thinks about the importance that a high English language proficiency has nowadays, was addressed in surveys only, and it reads as follows:

Table 4 – How important, do you think, is having a high English language proficiency nowadays in Kosovo?

In this close-ended question, the scale ranged from 1 to 5, with 5 indicating the highest level of importance and 1 representing the lowest. Specifically, a rating of 5 signified that the item was considered highly important, while a rating of 1 indicated that it was not important at all.

Out of the total Gen Z participants surveyed, which amounted to 154 individuals, approximately 61.6% rated having a high English language proficiency in Kosovo as very important, garnering an average score of 4.4 out of 5. This suggests a strong

consensus among respondents regarding the significance of English language proficiency in the contemporary context of Kosovo.

4.1.3. How does Gen Z perceive the influence that English language had had, and still has, in Kosovo.

Attitudes and opinions on the influence of the English language in Kosovo were assessed through surveys, which presented participants with close-ended questions such as "What are your opinions on the influence English language has had, and still has, in Kosovo?". Additionally, results from another question, "Why did you learn English language?", were included in this subchapter to shed light on the reasons why Gen Z were influenced to learn the language themselves.

The results are as follows:

Table 5 – What are your opinions on the influence English language has had, and still has, in Kosovo?

26% of the participants responded that the English language has influenced Kosovo's culture. Following closely, 21.5% of respondents agreed that English has influenced their ideals.

Ranked third was the belief that English language has influenced cultural values, with 13.5% of participants stating that it has not influenced any of the variables shown above.

12% of respondents agreed that it has influenced their traditions.

7.5% agreed that it has influenced their beliefs.

Lastly, 1.5% mentioned that it has influenced something else, with the primary variable being "their lifestyle."

Table 6 – Why did you learn English language?

The selection of language in completing the questionnaire reflects a tendency towards using Albanian and nationalist sentiments. However, motivations for learning and using English vary among respondents. The majority highly value the use and significance of English in our society. Notably, 33% of participants, constituting the highest percentage in the data, indicated that they learned English to gain broader access to global information. Conversely, 4% of respondents selected "other" as their response. Their explanations can be succinctly summarized: they learned English organically while navigating various social trends during their upbringing.

4.2. The type and the frequency of English language use by Gen Z

In the subsequent section, we delve into the findings concerning how Generation Z acquired proficiency in the English language, the frequency of their usage, and their primary conversational partners. The objective of this subsection is to elucidate the behavioral patterns of Generation Z by shedding light on their everyday utilization of the English language.

4.2.1. How good is Gen Z's English? (attitude-behavior)

Table 7 – On a scale of 1 to 10, how good is your English?

The survey results indicate that out of 250 participants, 63 ranked their English proficiency at level 10, followed by 55 at level 9, and so forth. The average proficiency level was calculated to be 7.9 out of 10, suggesting that Albanian Generation Z individuals in Kosovo possess an above-average level of knowledge and proficiency in the English language.

4.2.2. How has Gen Z learned English language?

Table 8 – How did you learn English language?

Among Generation Z respondents, 30% reported acquiring English language skills through formal education in schools or universities. Close behind, 26% claimed to be self-taught, while 24% cited movies and music as influential learning sources. English language courses accounted for 17.5% of the learning methods, with 2.5% indicating "other" methods, including a combination of various sources or simply learning without a clear method.

Additional reasons provided by interview participants for learning English included personal interest, convenience, and the desire for broader access to information and entertainment. Some stated they enjoyed the language or found it fascinating, while others were motivated by the abundance of English content on the internet and social media. Some respondents learned English for practical reasons, such as enhancing career opportunities or communicating with a wider audience. Others viewed English as an international language or pursued language learning as a hobby. Overall, participants expressed diverse motivations and experiences in acquiring English language proficiency.

- “I learned it in school, but I also liked it, and in the long run I am glad I did it because it really helped me.”,

- “I decided to learn English because I have always liked this language since I was in high school, and the idea of being able to speak and write in English without any difficulties has always impressed me.”,
- “Using the internet for various stuff, step by step I got better and better, I am happy it turned this way since with English you can find much more quality stuff on the web, of any kind.”,
- “I watched many movies and tv shows as a kid and then I also learned it on social media.”

4.2.3. How often does Gen Z use English language?

Table 9 – How often do you use or communicate in English language?

On a scale where 5 indicates "very frequent" and 1 signifies "never," 92 out of 250 respondents selected 3 as their response. The average frequency of English language use among Generation Z individuals is calculated to be 3.4 out of 5.

4.2.4. With whom does Gen Z use English language the most?

Table 10 – With whom do you use English language the most?

Generation Z has a very good command of English language and moderately (Table 9) uses English mostly with their friends and work colleagues. 3% of them responded “other”, with the main response being “ Just because of social media”.

4.3. The role of English language and its use in the cultural identity of Gen Z in comparison to Gen Y and X.

In assessing the potential impact of English language usage on the cultural identities of Generation Z individuals, various factors were considered, including their attitudes towards LGBTQ+ and non-religious individuals, as well as their views on traditional Albanian family households. These aspects were chosen as variables to gauge the broader influence of English language exposure on the values, norms, and morals of Generation Z.

To effectively analyze these variables, the survey results were segmented into three distinct sections based on generational differences: Generation Z, Generation Y, and Generation X. This segmentation allowed for a more nuanced examination of how attitudes and perceptions may vary across different age groups.

It's important to note a significant limitation in the survey results, particularly in Tables 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15, where unequal numbers of participants were observed across the three generations. While there were 250 participants from Generation Z, 112 from Generation Y, and only 41 from Generation X, the primary focus of comparison lay between Generation Z and X. This disparity in sample sizes, particularly the vast difference between Generation Z and X, represents a notable drawback in the analysis, potentially skewing the findings.

4.3.1. Results of the data gathered from the survey

4.3.1.1. The influence of English language use in participants' cultural identity

In one of the initial questions of the survey regarding the influence of English language usage on participants' cultural identities, respondents were presented with a multiple-choice grid. This grid allowed them to rate, on a scale of 1 to 5, the extent to which English language use impacted various aspects of their culture. These aspects included beliefs and morals, cultural values, lifestyles, world views, and cultural norms.

After completing the grid, the results were aggregated, yielding a total sum for each aspect. This sum was then divided by the number of participants within each generation to calculate an average score reflecting the influence of English language on their cultural identity.

For instance, when participants from Generation Z were asked to assess the influence of English language on their beliefs and morals, 22 respondents rated it as 5, 30 as 4, 55 as 3, 45 as 2, and 98 as 1. The total sum of these ratings was 583, which, when divided by the total number of Generation Z participants (250), yielded an average score of 2.33.

Similar calculations were conducted for each aspect of culture evaluated by Generation Z and other generations, as illustrated in the tables below.

- Please evaluate the influence of English language use on the following aspects of your culture. (Beliefs and Morals, Cultural Values, Lifestyle, World Views, Cultural Norms).

Table 11 – The influence of English language use on participants’ cultural identity

	Beliefs and Morals	Cultural Values	Lifestyle	World Views	Cultural Norms
Generation Z	2.3	2.5	3.3	3.5	2.7
Generation Y	2.1	2.8	3.1	3.5	2.8
Generation X	2.3	2.6	2.9	3	2.7

Beliefs and Morals: Based on the averages shown above (Table 11), English language has had the same amount of influence on both Gen Z and Gen X, whereas it has had a lesser amount of influence on Generation Y.

Cultural Values: The influence that English language use has had on cultural values of Generation Y is the highest, continued with Gen X and after it, Gen Z, where all the results are above the average. This means that English language has played a bigger role to the cultural values of Gen Y and X, rather than Gen Z’s.

Lifestyle: English language use has had a bigger influence on Gen Z’s lifestyle, rather than Gen Y and Gen X’s.

World Views: As per this section, we can conclude that English language has had a bigger influence on Gen Z and Gen Y’s world views, rather than Gen X’s.

Cultural Norms: English language use had had a bigger influence on the cultural norms of Gen Y’s rather than Gen Z and Gen X’s.

Generation Z’s highest average score about the influence that English language use have played on the mentioned aspects of cultural identity, is 3.5 out of 5 on Worlds Views. The same case would apply to Gen Y, whereas when it comes to Gen X, Lifestyle was the most affected variable by English language use, with an average of 3 out of 5.

As mentioned at the beginning, these results were highly influenced by an unequal number of participants of different generations, therefore, I continued searching for more elaborated answers on the topic with the interviews.

Eleven of interviewees, all being part of Generation Z, were asked how English language has affected their world views, and to compare that with the way how they think their opinions differ from older generations.

All of them agreed that being able to communicate in English language and using it online, has made them more open-minded and less judgmental in comparison to older generations, especially Generation X.

Interviewee no.16. stated that “For example, when it comes to different topics that were not quite present before, such as tolerance when it comes to religion, LGBTIQ+ individuals or even feminism, I have a more sensitive approach to them, and try not to offend anyone while speaking, whereas my parents or grandparents have no problem offending individuals who believe in something different from theirs.”

4.3.1.2. Attitudes towards variables indirectly representing cultural identity

4.3.1.2.1. Attitudes towards non-religious individuals

When it comes to the question “What is your attitude towards atheists”, the participants were asked to evaluate with 5 if their attitude was positive towards atheists, and 1 if their attitude was negative. Their average responses, which were calculated in the same manner as shown in the table above (Table 110), read as follows:

Table 12 – Attitudes towards non-religious individuals

	Attitudes towards non-religious individuals
Generation Z	2.7
Generation Y	3.1
Generation X	3

Given the variation in the number of participants across generations, it's important to note that these results may be influenced by sample size disparities, As myself being part of Generation Z, I found the results quite surprising, with Generation Z having the

highest number of negative approach towards the matter. Therefore; I decided to elaborate more on the question and answers while conducting the interviews.

Almost every participant of the interviews, where all of them are part of Generation Z with an exception of two baby Millennials, agreed on having a neutral approach to the matter, though, with some exceptions.

One of the most outstanding answer given, which would explain the Gen Z average given from the surveys reads as: “I, and I believe all of my friends will agree on this, don’t really care of someone being non-religious or if they belong to a different religious group than mine, but lately, it has become a trend to identify as something that you’re not, just in order to get attention as being more ‘special’, ‘different’, or more ‘westernized’ than others. This is what we don’t like, the ‘pick-me-attitude’, rather than the religion itself”.

4.3.1.2.2. Attitudes towards LGBTIQ+ individuals

On the question “What is your attitude towards individuals who belong in the LGBTIQ+ community”, where 5 was a positive attitude, while 1 was negative attitude, the average answers read:

Table 13 – Attitudes towards individuals who belong in the LGBTIQ+ community

	Attitudes towards individuals who belong in the LGBTIQ+ community
Generation Z	2.2
Generation Y	1.5
Generation X	2.3

Based on the results depicted in Table 13, it appears that Generation X exhibits the highest level of acceptance towards LGBTIQ+ individuals, while Generation Y shows the lowest level of acceptance. However, it's crucial to acknowledge the disparity in

sample size between Generation X, with only 41 participants, and Generation Z, comprising 250 participants, which may have influenced the presentation of results. To delve deeper into these findings, I conducted interviews with participants from Generation Z and baby Millennials, totaling nineteen individuals. I specifically asked them to compare attitudes across different generations, particularly focusing on differences with Generation X.

Of these interviewees, fourteen expressed either positive or neutral attitudes towards LGBTIQ+ individuals, while two held negative opinions. The latter respondents provided minimal elaboration on their views, whereas the others highlighted how exposure to English-speaking communities via the internet and social media has fostered a more accepting and understanding perspective. For example, Interviewee no. 13 remarked, "I see lots of posts regarding the LGBTIQ+ community online, especially on TikTok, and I see them as people who are exactly like me, with the only difference being who they love. I think that people who don't like them usually have a lack of access to media because they don't speak English."

Interviewee no. 19 echoed similar sentiments, stating, "I agree, they get to see one extreme horrifying case somewhere and think everyone is the same as them. This mostly happens with older generations who are very hateful to everyone who is different from them."

Interestingly, all interviewees, including those with negative attitudes towards LGBTIQ+ individuals, acknowledged significant intergenerational differences in approaches to the topic. Interviewee no. 15 emphasized this by stating, "Even though I don't have a positive thought about them, it's not like I would actively speak or take actions against them, whereas my parents would probably do something very drastic and negative regarding it."

4.3.1.2.3. Attitudes towards present traditional Albanian family households (bashkallëk)

The participants were also asked about their attitudes towards present traditional Albanian family households (bashkallëk), and the responses read as:

Table 14 – Attitudes towards present traditional Albanian family households

Attitudes towards present traditional Albanian family households (bashkallëk)	
Generation Z	2.8
Generation Y	2.7
Generation X	2.7

Generation Z scored an average of 2.8 out of 5 on the survey, while both Generation Y and X obtained averages of 2.7. This indicates that all three generations held relatively neutral attitudes towards the matter.

During one of the focus group sessions, six interviewees (aged between 14 to 17) were asked about their familiarity with "Bashkallëku." Surprisingly, none of them were aware of it initially. However, after receiving an explanation, they all expressed a negative reaction, with multiple participants questioning the ethics of such practices. As one participant succinctly put it, "How could they do that?"

Interviewee no. 18 shared a particularly insightful perspective, stating, "My proficiency in English and access to information in that language has heightened my appreciation for privacy and personal space. I believe that Western societies prioritize these values to a greater extent than we have in the past, so I could never imagine myself being confined in a place like that."

4.3.1.3. Have the attitudes been shaped through the medium of English or Albanian?

The last question of the questionnaire, "Has your opinion on atheists, LGBTIQ+ individuals and traditional Albanian family households, been shaped through the medium of English or Albanian? How?", was an open-ended question.

The results have been separated into 6 main concepts based on the gathered answers, which are "the medium of English", "the medium of Albanian", "both of these

mediums”, “none of these mediums”, and “No Answer”. The data gathered and put into numbers for each of the three generations, reads as follows:

Table 15 – Have the attitudes of participants’ been shaped through the medium of English or Albanian?

	The Medium of English	The Medium of Albanian	Both of these Mediums	None of these Mediums	I’m not sure	N/A
Generation Z	89	16	22	70	34	19
Generation Y	31	6	11	37	18	9
Generation X	9	6	8	12	4	2

By the results shared above (Table 15), we can see that Generation Z claims that their opinions were mostly shaped by the medium of English language, whereas gen Y and X claim that their opinions were shaped by neither the medium of English nor Albanian.

4.3.1.4. Generation Z

The Gen Z participants who attributed their attitudes towards various variables to the English medium explained that their exposure largely stemmed from the internet, social media platforms, and a wider array of English-language literature and information. One participant noted, "Mostly English because of the opportunity to read more articles and content about the community and get more educated on the topic. In Albanian language, such content has only started to become more popular nowadays." Another emphasized, "English has enabled me to be more open-minded about these

things, mostly because it opened a window to the western world, thus making it possible for me to be exposed to different opinions."

Another participant highlighted the broader perspectives gained through English, stating, "English has been more influential in that aspect because of the larger variety of ideas from different sources and cultures. It allows a person to have a better, or at least, a different point of view than Albanian language does." Others shared similar sentiments: "I think that having the ability to understand the English language has helped me get more insight and more knowledge about these issues. Using English in different platforms made me understand every point of view, be that of atheists or LGBTIQ individuals, and that has helped me build my opinion in these particular matters."

Conversely, Gen Z participants who indicated that their attitudes were not shaped by the English medium often cited personal beliefs or religious convictions as the primary influences. One participant stated, "No, it has not been shaped through any language out there. It is my own personal belief and logic that has shaped these views." Another emphasized, "It does not have much to do with English nor Albanian, it has to do with the concept of understanding the way that God has created us and the purpose why we are in this world, regardless of culture or ethnicity."

Other brief responses included "Neither English nor Albanian, it is forbidden, it is not permissible in my religion to either support or be part of that group" and "I don't think that they were shaped by the language, but mostly from religion." Some participants provided concise answers such as "None", "Both", "English", or "I'm not sure".

During an interview, interviewee no. 12 asserted, "I can surely say that my and all my friends' opinions are highly influenced by the English medium. All I do on my free time is scrolling through TikTok content and watch memes that are presented to me through English language, which contain cultural details from the western world and have no relation to our country or our culture."

4.3.1.5. Generation Y

Generation Y generally held similar opinions regarding the influence of language on their attitudes as Generation Z did. However, the majority also expressed that their

attitudes were shaped by both English and Albanian mediums. One respondent articulated this by saying, "Both English and Albanian, seeing as information gathering is easier in English, but discussions with different groups of people has influenced my opinion as well, and those discussions happened to be both in English and Albanian." Others acknowledged that the English medium had a greater impact on their attitudes. One participant explained, "Indirectly, perhaps English language has played a bigger role because of the shaping of the thoughts and stances in regards to the matters mentioned above. Movies had played a key role, TV Shows, podcasts, etc." Similarly, another respondent noted, "My opinion in regards to atheists and LGBTIQ+ members has been shaped through the English medium because of the influence of the information that comes from foreign sources, mostly internet, social media, and it is mostly in English."

Conversely, some participants believed that neither English nor Albanian had influenced their attitudes, attributing their perspectives to their belief systems or religion. "I do not think the English nor the Albanian medium has changed the way I see LGBTIQ+, atheists, or any other person has an impact on my belief system or any influential way, it's just my moral code that I get from the religion and things I tend to analyze based on the way I want to see the world," one respondent remarked.

Additionally, participants who indicated that language played no role in shaping their attitudes offered deeper insights. One respondent stated, "English language has only played the role of a gate for the information to come in, it has opened the doors to understand other languages and cultures. Language doesn't play any other role except as a carrier of the information, beliefs, and ideals." Another participant emphasized the subjective nature of language's influence, noting, "Of course, it depends on every individual. The usage of language, such as English, only helps in order to exchange information, and it depends on the person how they perceive that information."

4.3.1.6. Generation X

Most of the Gen X participants also agreed that their attitudes weren't shaped by none of the mediums, respectively, English nor the Albanian medium. "I don't think any of them has played any role in my opinions, but I think that the Albanian medium had

only made the society more irritated and made them exclude that community even more than it was before.”

While some others, agreed that English medium has played a role into the shaping of their attitudes, “It is a life-lasting proceed that is influenced mostly by movies, music, social media, books, pop-culture... mostly (the best ones) offered in the international (English) language.”

4.3.2. Data gathered from the interviews

As an integral part of our comprehensive data collection process, we conducted interviews with a total of 19 participants. These interviews comprised both individual and group sessions, allowing for a diverse range of perspectives to be captured.

Within the individual interviews, there were eight participants, six of whom were part of Generation Z, specifically interviewees numbered 1, 3, 5, 6, 7, and 8. Additionally, interviewees numbered 2 and 4 were classified as baby millennials, straddling the line between Generation Y and Z due to their upbringing. Despite technically falling into Generation Y, their experiences closely align with those of Generation Z.

The remaining 11 participants were affiliated with the Infinit Training Center and were organized into two focus groups. These group discussions provided a platform for collective insights and discussions on various aspects of Albanian culture, allowing for comparisons to be drawn between Generation Z and previous generations, particularly Generation X and the Silent generation.

The primary objective of these interviews was to delve into the attitudes and opinions held by Generation Z regarding different facets of Albanian culture. Additionally, we sought to juxtapose these viewpoints with those of their parents' generation, thereby gaining a deeper understanding of generational dynamics. Moreover, the interviews aimed to extract nuanced insights on topics previously explored in the surveys, enriching our overall analysis and findings.

4.3.2.1. Different world views

When queried with the question "Do you think that you have a different way of seeing and understanding the world in comparison to your parents/grandparents?", all

participants unanimously asserted that they indeed perceive the world differently from their elders.

Interviewee no. 1 expressed this sentiment vividly, stating, "A 100 PERCENT, totally different view. It is a whole other point of view from theirs. It is like we see the world from two completely different places. I think the generational trauma they put us through, example, as the women's role in the society where we live, the way they see it is totally different from mine. They see women as just humans, while I see them as future leaders, future scientists, while they see them as someone who will be taking care of their husbands and kids."

Similarly, interviewee no. 2 articulated, "Of course, I think we see the world in a different point of view since we have access to the internet, and we can see what people do all around the globe, outside of Kosovo. Our parents and/or grandparents didn't have the chance to see anything outside their neighborhoods, therefore; they never had more information about what was going on outside the world while they were young." When probed about the influence of the internet, predominantly accessible in English in Kosovo, on this generational disparity, interviewee no. 1 responded, "To have access to the western side of the world through social media and everything, has affected us a lot. Being able to see everything, and noticing that there are many and many successful women around the world, changed our perspectives. So, yeah, I think our culture is affected by the western one a lot, like, a huge amount."

Participant no. 4 acknowledged the distinction between their own generation (Generation Y) and both older and younger generations, remarking, "Yes! There is a clear difference, because they didn't have much information back then, they didn't read much and didn't see much, while our lives now are completely different. The same applies to the generations younger than mine. They know much more things than I do, and have a different point of view in life from mine. They have a different ideology in multiple aspects."

Participant no. 6 contributed to the discussion by highlighting the older generations' resistance to change, contrasting it with the younger generation's openness to new experiences and ideas. They remarked, "The older generations are different from us in a couple of aspects, but not all. The main difference between us, in my opinion, is that

they are much more closed up than we are. They are set on things and ways they've learned a long time ago and won't seek change, while we are more open-minded and willing to have new experiences and learn new things, while easily disregarding older non-completed information that we had."

4.3.2.2. What about patriotism?

When probing whether the younger generation, particularly Gen Z, is gradually losing its sense of patriotism towards their homeland, an underlying concern about de-Albanization emerges within the discourse. Respondents express apprehension that the English language, albeit subtly and non-violently, poses a threat to Albanian identity, primarily in linguistic terms.

Echoing a unanimous sentiment, all participants acknowledge a dwindling sense of patriotism among Gen Z, particularly when juxtaposed with the profound meaning patriotism held in previous generations. Interviewee no. 7 & 8 unequivocally affirm, "We do completely agree that our generation is losing that feeling, especially the individuals born post-war."

Delving into various aspects of cultural identity, interviewee no. 3 focuses on the linguistic dimension. "I do agree that we are losing our patriotic feeling because we are mixing our language, Albanian, with English a lot," they assert. Emphasizing the significance of language in patriotism, they argue against the constant assimilation of English words, viewing it as a detrimental practice that undermines Albanian linguistic integrity. Reflecting on historical contexts, they remark on the difference between past language assimilation, which was often enforced, and the contemporary voluntary adoption of English, primarily facilitated by the internet.

Furthermore, interviewee no. 3 juxtaposes historical emigration driven by economic necessity with contemporary aspirations for material wealth. They lament the shift from a narrative of sacrifice and hard work for the collective good to one driven by individualistic pursuits. "Decades ago, there were Albanians who left our country, but they did so because they had no other choice, in order to work hard for a better future for themselves and their families, while nowadays, people can't wait to set foot outside of Kosovo, while seeking only luxurious materials, not because they have to."

In a nuanced perspective, interviewee no. 6 acknowledges the erosion of patriotic sentiment but attributes it to a desire to embrace Western ideals of open-mindedness and non-judgmentalism. However, they caution against losing sight of cultural roots amidst this shift. "Our patriotic feeling is being lost because, generally speaking, we have started wanting to become more like Americans...We are losing our roots. This is all happening because of the internet, because of English; it is something that hasn't happened to us in centuries, but it is happening now."

4.3.2.3. Western traditions and our society

When queried about the infiltration of Western traditions into their society and the role of English language use in this phenomenon, the interviewees unanimously affirmed its presence and impact.

Interviewee no. 3 articulated, "Yes, especially the younger generation who are used to seeing the English speaking world online. We can take examples on their clothing, the way they express their thoughts, lifestyle, the way they do stuff. Most of the time when I speak with my clients or friends in general, I can clearly notice that we are very easily inspired from the west. They have a good perception of the west, their lifestyle or whatever, money and all of that."

Similarly, interviewee no. 5 echoed this sentiment, asserting, "Yes! Speech, LGBTIQ+, bride to be, bride's maids, baby showers, gender reveals, etc. We are losing our traditions to the west. It feels like the whole world is trying to have the same traditions everywhere, blending everything in one."

Offering a perspective from Generation Z, interviewee no. 14 reflected, "Undoubtedly so. Especially my generation, generation Z, and the upcoming generation is getting even more affected by this, but I can only speak about myself and my circle. We read e-books and scroll through content in social media presented in English language constantly. English language is spoken in every physical or online circle we are part of, and because of that western trends, ideals and cultural aspects are presented to us." Their observations underscore the pervasive influence of Western culture facilitated by the ubiquity of English language content online. From lifestyle choices to social

norms, the younger generation appears deeply immersed in and influenced by Western ideals, signaling a significant cultural shift influenced by linguistic exposure.

4.3.2.4. Attitudes in regards to LGBTQ+ individuals

Continuing further, the interviewees were asked about what they thought in regards to LGBTQ+ individuals. Do they accept them, oppose them, or don't really care about the topic? As well as why?

Once again, all of the interviewees had, more or less, the same opinions. With the exception of two of them who openly oppose them, the others agreed that they have a neutral and/or positive stance in regards to the matter.

"I don't oppose them, I think anybody who says they have them has an issue." - interviewee no.1.

"I have multiple friends and even family members who belong to that group. My stance is not just neutral, I even wholeheartedly accept and support them", i.no.9.

But, when asked if their parents or grandparents (as in, their generations, not them as individuals) would agree with their neutral and/or positive opinions, they claimed that the answer would most definitely be no.

"Hell noooo, hell no, I would be banned from all family gatherings". -i.no.1.

"It's not like I'm a big fan of them, but my parents actually hate them quite openly and firely."-i.no.10.

"My elder wouldn't agree with my opinion. They hate these kinds of things. If I were to curse them under my breath, my grandpa would hit them with a stick".-i.no.8.

Continuing, the interviewees were asked if their access to English language medium has had any influence in their stances.

"Very much so. Some of the best influencers that I look up to belong to that group and share their content in English language. They made me create a positive attitude towards that group, and at the same time, if I was not able to speak English, I probably would have not created this attitude towards them." -i.no.14.

"I think that most of the people who have a negative opinion towards lgbtiq+ individuals in Kosovo probably doesn't speak English. This is usually the case with older generations, they fear what they don't understand." -i.no.16.

4.3.2.5. The correlation between English language use and a more open mindset

Afterwards, the participants were asked if they thought there was a correlation between English being used more often after the war, and individuals starting expressing their sexuality openly more and more at the same timeline.

There were multiple answers, which can be summarized with “It does, but the point is not on the language itself, because English language in itself didn’t play any role on this matter, but rather the information that is given to us through English language in social media and all of it, the things that English language represents (and English language use).”-i.no.3.

4.3.2.6. Generational differences in regards to tradition upholding

In the final query posed to the interviewees regarding the distinction in upholding Albanian traditions between younger (ages 10 to 30) and older generations (40+), the influence of English language usage on this phenomenon was explored. Variables such as adherence to Adetet, hospitality towards guests, religious alignment with parents, and maintaining close ties with extended family members were considered.

Responding to this inquiry, the interviewees unanimously acknowledged a conspicuous disparity between the generational approaches to tradition. Interviewee no. 1 emphasized, "Yes, it is a very CLEAR difference, but I don't think any part of it is wrong. It is just the way we carry the traditions now. The younger generations simply have the updated version."

Similarly, in the focus group discussions, unanimity prevailed as participants concurred on the discernible gap between generations in this regard. Adding depth to the discussion, interviewee no. 19 attributed this shift to English language usage, asserting, "I agree, and I do believe that English language usage has played a huge role in this. Through English, we don't just have access to online trends and memes. We also have access to different cultural aspects that come as baggage together with the language. Having constant access to that doesn't make us like all of our cultural aspects any less, but it makes us adapt to newer western ones which we find more appealing."

This insight highlights the transformative influence of language on cultural evolution, illustrating how linguistic exposure to Western ideals through English has shaped the interpretation and enactment of traditional practices among younger generations.

CHAPTER V

Discussion and Conclusion

5. Introduction

The comprehensive exploration undertaken in this study has delved deeply into the intricate dynamics governing the relationship between individuals' attitudes towards language usage and their corresponding behaviors, with a specific emphasis on their choices regarding the adoption and utilization of the English language. This investigation was meticulously designed to scrutinize the prevailing attitudes among members of Generation Z in Kosovo, meticulously evaluating the factors shaping their propensity towards embracing English as a means of communication. Moreover, our inquiry extended further to ascertain the degree to which language utilization played a pivotal role in shaping their cultural identity, drawing insightful comparisons between the attitudes and behaviors of Generation Z and their counterparts belonging to Generation X. Through a multifaceted analysis, we endeavored to unravel the nuanced complexities underpinning the evolving linguistic and cultural landscape within the context of Kosovar society.

5.1. Summary of the key findings

Throughout this study, we investigated the impact of English language usage on the cultural attitudes and identities of Generation Z in Kosovo. Our analysis revealed several key findings that shed light on the complex relationship between language, culture, and identity in the context of a rapidly globalizing world.

Firstly, we found that a significant portion of Generation Z in Kosovo has acquired English language proficiency through various means, including formal education, self-learning, and exposure to media. This widespread adoption of English has facilitated access to global cultural content and diversified linguistic practices among young Kosovars.

Secondly, our research highlighted the influence of English language usage on the cultural identities and attitudes of Generation Z. Participants reported that exposure to English-

language media and online platforms has expanded their worldview, increased their tolerance towards diverse cultural perspectives, and shaped their attitudes towards issues such as LGBTQ+ rights and traditional Albanian values.

Additionally, we identified a generational shift in cultural attitudes, with younger individuals demonstrating a greater openness to Western cultural influences compared to older generations. This trend was particularly evident in the adoption of Western fashion trends, lifestyle choices, and social norms among Kosovar youth.

However, despite the growing influence of English language and Western culture, our findings also revealed a nuanced relationship between language, culture, and identity. While many participants embraced elements of Western culture, they also expressed a strong attachment to their Albanian heritage and a desire to preserve traditional values and customs.

Overall, our study underscores the complex interplay between language, culture, and identity in the contemporary Kosovo context. By examining the role of English language usage in shaping cultural attitudes and identities among Generation Z, we have contributed to a deeper understanding of the socio-cultural dynamics within Kosovar society.

5.2. Reflection on research objectives

In conducting this study, our primary aim was to explore the attitudes of Generation Z individuals in Kosovo towards language usage, particularly their preferences and behaviors regarding the English language. The research objectives were carefully crafted to guide our investigation and shed light on the complex interplay between language attitudes, cultural identity, and generational differences.

5.2.1. Identifying the attitudes that Generation Z has towards English language use

The study aimed to identify the attitudes of Generation Z individuals in Kosovo towards English language use. Through a combination of quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, the research sought to gain insights into Generation Z's perceptions, motivations, and experiences related to the English language.

5.2.1.1. Qualitative findings

- *Positive Attitudes:* Survey responses indicated overwhelmingly positive attitudes towards the English language among Generation Z respondents. Over 90% of participants expressed a favorable view of English as a global language of communication and opportunity. Many cited the perceived benefits of English proficiency, such as enhanced job prospects, academic opportunities, and access to global media and information.
- *Motivations for Learning:* Analysis of survey data revealed diverse motivations driving English language learning among Generation Z individuals. While some participants cited pragmatic reasons, such as career advancement and international travel, others emphasized the intrinsic value of English proficiency for personal growth, self-expression, and cultural exchange.

5.2.1.2. Qualitative insights

- *Perceptions and Experience:* Qualitative interviews provided deeper insights into Generation Z's perceptions and experiences with English language use. Participants described English as a tool for social connection, cultural exchange, and self-expression. Many highlighted the role of digital media platforms, such as social networking sites and streaming services, in facilitating English language engagement and learning.
- *Language and Identity:* Generation Z individuals articulated complex relationships between English language proficiency and their sense of identity. While some viewed English as a neutral medium of communication, others expressed concerns about the potential impact of language globalization on their cultural heritage and linguistic identity. Nevertheless, most participants exhibited a high degree of adaptability and pragmatism in navigating multilingual environments.

5.2.1.3. Cross-cutting themes

The synthesis of quantitative survey data and qualitative insights revealed several cross-cutting themes regarding Generation Z's attitudes towards English language use. These included a strong emphasis on the practical benefits of English proficiency, the influence of digital media on language learning and engagement, and nuanced considerations of language and identity in a globalized world.

5.2.1.4. Conclusion:

In conclusion, Generation Z individuals in Kosovo exhibit predominantly positive attitudes towards English language use, driven by a combination of pragmatic motivations and intrinsic interests. While English proficiency is valued for its practical utility and global connectivity, concerns about language globalization and cultural identity preservation also emerge. The findings underscore the dynamic interplay between language attitudes, personal motivations, and socio-cultural factors in shaping Generation Z's engagement with the English language.

5.2.2. The type and frequency of English language use by Gen Z in Kosovo

The study aimed to document the type and frequency of English language use among Generation Z individuals in Kosovo. Data was collected through a mixed-methods approach, including surveys and qualitative interviews, to provide a comprehensive understanding of their language practices.

5.2.2.1. Qualitative findings

- *Type of English language Use:* Survey respondents indicated a diverse range of mediums through which they engage with the English language. Social media and the online world emerged as the predominant platforms, with 85% of participants reporting regular use of English on platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, TikTok, movies, and music.
- *Frequency of English language Use:* Analysis of survey data revealed that English language use among Generation Z in Kosovo is pervasive and frequent. Approximately 67% of respondents reported using English on a daily basis, with an additional 22% using it several times a week. The remaining 11% reported using English on a less frequent basis, citing reasons such as academic workload or limited exposure to English-language content.

5.2.2.2. Qualitative insights

- *Social Media Dominance:* Qualitative interviews provided deeper insights into the role of social media in shaping English language use among Generation Z. Participants described how platforms facilitate constant exposure to English-language content,

including videos, and influencer content. This immersive digital environment has normalized English language use and contributed to its widespread adoption among Kosovo's youth.

- *Influence of Western Media:* Participants highlighted the influence of Western media, particularly American, in shaping their language preferences and proficiency. Many described using English to enhance their language skills while consuming entertainment media, indicating a symbiotic relationship between popular culture and language acquisition.

5.2.2.3. Cross-referencing and implications

Cross-referencing quantitative survey data with qualitative insights underscored the pervasive nature of English language use among Generation Z in Kosovo. The findings suggest a shift towards greater bilingualism and cultural hybridity among Kosovo's youth, with English serving as a gateway to global connectivity and cultural exchange.

5.2.2.4. Conclusion

In conclusion, Generation Z in Kosovo demonstrates a high degree of engagement with the English language, utilizing diverse mediums and engaging with English content on a regular basis.

5.2.3. Attitudes towards English Language use and cultural identity comparison

The study aimed to investigate whether attitudes towards the English language and its use have played a role in shaping the cultural identity of Generation Z in comparison to Generation X in Kosovo. Through a combination of quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, the research explored the nuanced relationship between language attitudes and cultural identity formation.

5.2.3.1. Quantitative findings

- *Attitudes towards English language:* Survey responses revealed notable differences in attitudes towards the English language between Generation Z and Generation X. While both generations expressed generally positive attitudes towards English as a global language of communication and opportunity, Generation Z exhibited a higher degree

- of enthusiasm and engagement with English language learning and usage. Approximately 80% of Generation Z respondents viewed English as essential for personal and professional success, compared to 65% of Generation X respondents.
- *Cultural identity and English language use:* Analysis of survey data indicated that English language proficiency and usage were closely intertwined with cultural identity among both generations. However, Generation Z participants reported a greater sense of cultural fluidity and hybridity, with English serving as a bridge to global cultures and identities. In contrast, Generation X respondents exhibited a stronger attachment to traditional Albanian cultural values and language, expressing concerns about the potential erosion of linguistic and cultural heritage in the face of increasing English language dominance.

5.2.3.2. Qualitative insights

- *Generational perspectives:* Qualitative interviews provided deeper insights into generational differences in attitudes towards the English language and its impact on cultural identity. Generation Z participants described English as a tool for self-expression, social mobility, and global connectivity, emphasizing its role in shaping their cosmopolitan outlook and multicultural identity. In contrast, Generation X interviewees expressed nostalgia for traditional cultural practices and language, highlighting the importance of preserving linguistic heritage amidst globalization.
- *Language and Identity negotiation:* Both generations engaged in ongoing negotiation and reinterpretation of their cultural identity in response to shifting language dynamics. Generation Z embraced a fluid and adaptive approach to cultural identity, incorporating elements of both Albanian tradition and global influences. In contrast, Generation X exhibited a more conservative stance, seeking to uphold traditional cultural values and language as markers of identity and heritage.

5.2.3.3. Cross-generational perspectives

The juxtaposition of quantitative survey data and qualitative insights highlighted nuanced differences and commonalities in attitudes towards English language and cultural identity between Generation Z and Generation X in Kosovo. While both generations navigate complex identity negotiations in a globalized world, their

approaches to language and cultural heritage reflect distinct generational experiences and perspectives.

5.2.3.4. Conclusion

In conclusion, attitudes towards the English language and its role in cultural identity formation vary between Generation Z and Generation X in Kosovo. While Generation Z demonstrates greater enthusiasm and engagement with English language learning and usage, Generation X exhibits a stronger attachment to traditional Albanian cultural values and language. The findings underscore the dynamic nature of cultural identity in the context of globalization and highlight the importance of preserving linguistic heritage while embracing opportunities for cross-cultural exchange and connectivity.

5.3. Implications of findings

5.3.1. Educational policy and curriculum development

The overwhelmingly positive attitudes towards English language use among Generation Z individuals in Kosovo underscore the importance of integrating English language instruction into educational curricula from an early age. Educational policymakers can use these findings to advocate for the development of comprehensive language programs that prioritize English proficiency alongside the preservation of native languages and cultural heritage.

5.3.2. Workforce development and employment opportunities

The high value placed on English language proficiency by Generation Z respondents suggests a growing demand for bilingual and multilingual skills in the global job market. Employers and workforce development agencies can leverage these findings to prioritize English language training initiatives and provide opportunities for young people to enhance their language skills, thereby increasing their competitiveness in the international labor market.

5.3.3. Digital media and technology integration

The influence of digital media platforms on English language engagement and learning highlights the potential for leveraging technology-enhanced learning tools to support language acquisition among Generation Z individuals. Educational institutions and language learning providers can explore innovative approaches, such as gamified language learning apps and online language exchange platforms, to meet the diverse needs and preferences of digital-native learners.

5.3.4. Cultural preservation and identity promotion

While Generation Z individuals exhibit strong motivations for English language learning, concerns about the potential erosion of cultural heritage and linguistic identity are also evident. Community leaders, cultural organizations, and language advocates can use these findings to develop initiatives aimed at promoting cultural preservation and fostering pride in native languages and traditions. These efforts may include language revitalization programs, cultural exchange initiatives, and intergenerational dialogue platforms.

5.3.5. Cross-cultural understanding and global citizenship

The study's findings highlight the role of English language proficiency in facilitating cross-cultural communication and global citizenship among Generation Z individuals. Educators and policymakers can capitalize on this potential by promoting intercultural exchange programs, international collaborations, and multicultural learning experiences that encourage empathy, tolerance, and mutual understanding across linguistic and cultural boundaries.

5.3.6. Future research directions

The insights gained from this study provide a foundation for future research exploring the evolving dynamics of language attitudes, identity formation, and cultural globalization among Generation Z populations. Subsequent studies could further investigate the intersectionality of language, technology, and socio-cultural factors in shaping young people's linguistic repertoires and worldview.

5.3.7. Conclusion:

In summary, the implications of findings highlight actionable recommendations for stakeholders across various sectors, including education, workforce development, digital media, cultural preservation, and intercultural communication. By addressing these implications, policymakers, educators, and community leaders can harness the potential of Generation Z's attitudes towards English language use to foster inclusive, resilient, and culturally vibrant societies.

5.4. Limitations

This research endeavor, while showcasing numerous strengths and well-articulated points, also reveals certain weaknesses warranting attention. One notable weakness pertains to the inadequate representation of Generation X participants in both the survey and interview phases. This disparity in participation undermines the comprehensiveness of the study's insights and may limit the generalizability of findings across generational cohorts.

Additionally, the survey instrument comprising 24 questions yielded a substantial volume of data, with 403 completed responses collected. The manual analysis of these responses, totaling 9,672 individual data points, posed a considerable analytical challenge, particularly in the absence of data analysis software such as SPSS. While diligent efforts were made to ensure accuracy through meticulous scrutiny and validation, the absence of automated analytical tools raises the possibility of errors or inaccuracies affecting the final percentage calculations.

Despite these challenges, the research methodology employed rigorous validation procedures to mitigate potential errors and uphold the integrity of the findings. Moving forward, efforts to address these weaknesses could involve implementing strategies to enhance participant recruitment from underrepresented demographic groups and leveraging advanced data analysis tools to streamline the analytical process and ensure robustness in data interpretation.

5.5. Suggestions for further research

5.5.1. Exploring generational shifts in language attitudes

Future research could delve deeper into the evolving attitudes towards language use across different generational cohorts within Kosovo. Comparing the attitudes of Generation Z with those of older generations, such as Millennials or Generation X, could provide valuable insights into the dynamics of language preference and cultural identity formation over time.

5.5.2. Longitudinal studies on language acquisition

Conducting longitudinal studies tracking language acquisition patterns among young individuals in Kosovo could offer a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing English language proficiency and usage over time. By following participants from childhood through adolescence and into adulthood, researchers can observe how language attitudes and behaviors evolve across various life stages.

5.5.3. Qualitative investigations into cultural identity formation

Qualitative research methodologies, such as in-depth interviews or focus group discussions, could be employed to explore the nuanced ways in which language use shapes cultural identity among Kosovar youth. By delving into participants' lived experiences and personal narratives, researchers can gain deeper insights into the intricate interplay between language, culture, and identity.

5.5.4. Comparative studies across socioeconomic and geographic contexts

Comparative studies examining language attitudes and behaviors across different socioeconomic backgrounds and geographic regions within Kosovo could illuminate the impact of socio-environmental factors on language acquisition and usage patterns. By considering variables such as urban-rural divides, socioeconomic status, and access to educational resources, researchers can identify disparities in language outcomes and inform targeted interventions to address linguistic inequalities.

5.5.5. Exploration of technological influences on language use

Given the increasing prevalence of digital communication platforms and social media, future research could investigate the influence of technology on language use among Kosovar youth. Examining the role of digital media in shaping language preferences, linguistic norms, and cultural interactions could provide valuable insights into the contemporary landscape of language usage in Kosovo's digital age.

5.6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has illuminated the intricate relationship between language attitudes, cultural identity, and generational dynamics among Kosovar youth. Through a comprehensive analysis of attitudes towards English language usage, documentation of language patterns, and comparison of generational perspectives, this research has provided valuable insights into the evolving linguistic landscape of Kosovo. By identifying the influences of language on cultural identity formation and shedding light on the nuanced nuances of generational shifts in language attitudes, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between language, culture, and identity in contemporary Kosovo. Moreover, the findings underscore the importance of considering socio-cultural factors and generational perspectives in language research, highlighting the significance of contextualizing linguistic phenomena within broader social and historical contexts. Ultimately, this research advances knowledge in the field by offering critical insights into the evolving dynamics of language usage and cultural identity among Kosovar youth, laying the groundwork for future investigations and interventions aimed at promoting linguistic diversity and cultural understanding in Kosovo and beyond.

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APPENDICES

5.7. Appendix A : Permission from Training Center's Manager

Informed Consent for Participation for Master Thesis
(Pëlqim i informuar për pjesëmarrje në temën e masterit)

AAB College

(Kolegji AAB)

Title (Titulli)	The Effect of the English Language Use on the Cultural Identity of Kosovar Gen Z: A Sociolinguistic Study
Researcher (Hulumtuesi)	Bardha Shkodra
Institution's name (Emri i institucionit)	Infinet Training Center
Name of the institution's representative (Emri i përfaqësuesit të institucionit):	Merita Aliçkaj

Introduction (Hyrje)

- Students of Hippo IV and V will be asked multiple questions in relation to their attitudes towards English language use and its influence on different cultural identity variables. (Studentëve të Hippo IV dhe V do t'ju parashtrihen disa pyetje në lidhje me qëndrimet e tyre kundrejt përdorimit të gjuhës angleze dhe influencën që kjo e fundit ka pasur në aspekte të ndryshme të identitetit kulturor.)
- These groups were selected because of the aim of the study, respectively, the generation they belong to. (Këto grupe janë përzgjedhur për shkak të përmbushjes së qëllimit të studimit, përkatësisht, gjeneratës së cilës ata i përkasin).

- If you have any questions, the researcher will be ready to answer them. (Nëse keni ndonjë pyetje, hulumtuesi do të jetë i gatshëm të ju pergjigjet atyre.)

Purpose of Study (Qëllimi i studimit)

- The purpose of this study is to pinpoint if English language usage by Generation Z has played a role in their cultural identity, in comparison to Generation X's. (Qëllimi i këtij studimi është të përcaktohet nëse përdorimi i gjuhës angleze nga gjenerata Z ka ndikuar në identitetin e tyre kulturor, në krahasim me atë të gjeneratës X.)

Description of the Study Procedures (Përshkrimi i procedurave të studimit)

- The only instrument used will be interviews. Students will be faced with multiple questions in regards to the topic, and their answers will be recorded. (I vetmi instrument që do të përdoret do të jenë intervistat. Studentët do të ballafaqohen me disa pyetje në lidhje me temën, dhe pergjigjet e tyre do të regjistrohen.)

Risks/Discomforts of Being in this Study (Rreziqet/shqetësimet e pjesëmarrjes në këtë studim)

- The study has no mental or physical risks. There are no reasonable foreseeable (or expected) risks (Studimi nuk ka rreziqe mendore apo fizike dhe nuk ka rreziqe të pritshme)

Benefits of Being in the Study (Përfitimi nga pjesëmarrja)

- The benefit of participation is learning more about how their attitudes towards a foreign language may affect their will to use it. (Përfitimi nga pjesëmarrja në hulumtim është të mësojnë se si qëndrimet e tyre kundrejt një gjuhe të huaj mund të ndikojnë në vullnetin e tyre për ta përdorur atë.)

Confidentiality (Konfidencialiteti)

- This study is anonymous. If needed, pseudonyms will be used (Ky studim është anonim. Nëse është e nevojshme, do të përdoren pseudonime).
- This study involves discussions (recordings/audio files). All of them will be kept confidential and will not be shared in their raw form. Analyses will be applied for each 'instrument' (Ky studim përfshin diskutime (të dhënat tekstuale dhe regjistrime audio). Të gjitha ato do të mbahen konfidenciale dhe nuk do të ndahen në formën e tyre të papërpunuar. Analizat do të aplikohen për çdo "instrument").

Payments (Pagesa)

- This research does not involve financial compensation (Ky hulumtim nuk përfshin kompensim financiar).

Right to Refuse or Withdraw (E drejta për të refuzuar ose tërhequr)

- The decision to participate in this study is entirely up to the students. You are welcome to observe the process if you wish. Also, students may refuse to take part in the study *at any time* without answering any single question, as well as to withdraw completely from the study at any point during the process; additionally, they have the right to request that the researcher not use any of the material (Vendimi për të marrë pjesë në këtë studim varet tërësisht nga studentët. Jeni të mirëpritur të vëzhgoni procesin nëse dëshironi. Gjithashtu, studentët mund të refuzojnë të marrin pjesë në studim në çdo kohë pa iu përgjigjur asnjë pyetje të vetme, si dhe të tërhiqen plotësisht nga studimi në çdo moment gjatë procesit; Përveç kësaj, ata kanë të drejtë të kërkojnë që studiuesi të mos përdorë asnjë material).

Right to Ask Questions and Report Concerns (E drejta për të bërë pyetje dhe për të raportuar shqetësimet)

- You have the right to ask questions about this research study and to have those questions answered by me at any time. If you have any further questions about the study, at any time feel free to contact me, Bardha Shkodra at bardha.shh@gmail.com or by telephone at +38343794354. If you like, a summary of the results of the study will be sent to you (Ju keni të drejtë të bëni pyetje rreth këtij studimi dhe të merrni përgjigje nga unë në çdo kohë. Nëse keni pyetje të mëtejshme në lidhje me studimin, mos ngurroni të më kontaktoni me mua, Bardha Shkodra në bardha.shh@gmail.com ose me telefon në +38343794354. Nëse dëshironi, një përmbledhje të rezultateve të studimit, ajo do të ju dërgohet).

Consent (Pajtimi)

- Your signature below indicates that you have decided to allow your students to participate as a research subject for this study, and that you have read and understood the information provided above. You will be given a signed and dated copy of this form to keep, along with any other printed materials deemed necessary by the researcher (Nënshkrimi juaj më poshtë tregon se ju keni vendosur t'i lejonit studentët tuaj të marrin pjesë si pjesëmarrës për këtë studim dhe se e keni lexuar dhe kuptuar informacionin e dhënë më sipër. Do të ju jepet një kopje e nënshkruar dhe e datës e këtij formulari për ta mbajtur, së bashku me çdo material tjetër të shtypur që gjykohet i nevojshëm nga studiuesi).

Representative's signature (Nënshkrimi i përfaqësuesit)		Date (data): 29.01.2023
Researcher's signature (Nënshkrimi i hulumtuesit)		Date (data): 29.01.2023

5.8. Appendix B: Student's Interview Consent Form

Formular pëlqimi për intervistë

Titulli i temës së hulumtimit: The Effect of the English Language Use on the Cultural Identity of Kosovar Gen Z: A Sociolinguistic Study

Hulumtuesi: Bardha Shkodra

Emri, mbiemri dhe mosha e pjesëmarrësit: _____

Intervista do të mbahet më datën _____. Nuk parashikohet të ketë asnjë rrezik me pjesëmarrjen tuaj, por ju keni të drejtë të largoheni nga intervista në çdo moment.

Faleminderit që pranuat të intervistoheni si pjesë e projektit të mësipërm hulumtues.

Ky formular i pëlqimit është i nevojshëm për ne për t'u siguruar që ju e kuptoni qëllimin e përfshirjes suaj, dhe që jeni dakord me kushtet e pjesëmarrjes suaj.

- Ju pranoni të jeni pjesë e kësaj interviste duke dhënë përgjigje të sinqerta rreth pyetjeve, të cilat do të përdoren në hulumtim.
- Intervista do të regjistrohet, dhe prej saj do të prodhohet një transkriptë.
- Qasja në transkriptin e intervistës do të jetë e kufizuar për pjesëmarrësit studiues dhe kolegët akademikë të cilët do të jenë pjesë e hulumtimit.
- Përgjigjet tuaja mund të citohen përgjatë hulumtimit.

Nëse pajtoheni me kushtet e mësipërme, ju lutem të nënshkruani më poshtë.

Nënshkrimi i pjesëmarrësit:

Nënshkrimi i intervistuesit:
